

Advancing Generalizability and Fairness in Breast MRI Tumour Segmentation and Treatment Response Prediction : Structured description of the challenge design

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Title

Use the title to convey the essential information on the challenge mission.

Advancing Generalizability and Fairness in Breast MRI Tumour Segmentation and Treatment Response Prediction

Challenge acronym

Preferable, provide a short acronym of the challenge (if any).

MAMA-MIA

Challenge abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Breast cancer remains the most common cancer among women and a leading cause of female mortality worldwide. Dynamic contrast-enhanced MRI (DCE-MRI) is a highly sensitive imaging modality for evaluating breast tumours, guiding pre-surgical treatment planning, and assessing therapeutic responses. Despite its growing adoption, a standardized benchmark for using DCE-MRI in breast cancer research—particularly for primary tumour segmentation and treatment response prediction—remains absent, hindering advancements in personalized care.

The MAMA-MIA Challenge addresses this gap by providing a comprehensive framework for two critical and complementary tasks: (1) segmentation of primary tumours in DCE-MRI and (2) prediction of pathological complete response (pCR) to neoadjuvant chemotherapy (NAC). This dual focus integrates imaging data with clinical outcomes to enhance tumour characterization and individualized treatment planning. The challenge also prioritizes generalizability and fairness, evaluating AI models not only for accuracy but also for equitable performance across medical centres and demographic subgroups, such as age, menopausal status, and breast density.

Participants will gain access to the largest homogenized DCE-MRI dataset to date, featuring 1506 annotated scans from over 20 centres, enriched with clinical variables like tumour subtype [1, 2]. External validation includes 574 cases from three distinct European centres (Spain, Lithuania, and Poland), showcasing diverse imaging protocols and clinical settings. By advancing tumour segmentation, treatment response prediction, and fairness, the challenge seeks to optimize NAC regimens, refine surgical planning, and set new standards for ethical AI in

medical imaging—driving innovation in breast cancer care.

Challenge keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the challenge.

breast cancer, tumour segmentation, pathological complete response, DCE-MRI, generalizability, fairness, personalized treatment, ethical AI, medical imaging, healthcare equity

Year

2025

Novelty of the challenge

Briefly describe the novelty of the challenge.

The MAMA-MIA Challenge aims to set a new benchmark for breast MRI analysis by addressing unmet clinical and technical needs in breast cancer research. It features the largest annotated dataset of pre-treatment DCE-MRI scans, with expert-segmented primary tumours and NAC treatment outcomes [1, 2]. The challenge uniquely integrates tumour segmentation and treatment response prediction into a dual-task framework, allowing participants to address complementary aspects of breast cancer care. This dual focus supports comprehensive treatment planning, including tumour characterization, surgical guidance, and prediction of NAC outcomes.

The challenge specifically evaluates two aspects of proposed algorithms to encourage applicability in diverse medical setups and population distributions:

1) Generalizability: The challenge training dataset features 1506 annotated DCE-MRI sequences from over 25 U.S.-based centres with diverse imaging protocols, vendors, and scanners. This extensive variability ensures a rich and heterogeneous training cohort. For external validation, the models will be evaluated on a separate cohort of 574 cases from three European centres (Spain, Lithuania, and Poland) with similar scanners, but different imaging protocols. This multi-site, multi-protocol design promotes the development of AI models that generalize well across diverse clinical environments.

2) Fairness: Models will be evaluated on their ability to perform equitably across variables like age, menopausal status, and breast density—factors known to influence breast cancer detection and treatment outcomes [3, 4]. For instance, models must address the challenges posed by higher breast density, which can reduce segmentation accuracy. By integrating fairness metrics, the challenge promotes the development of ethical AI systems capable of delivering consistent performance across diverse populations and demographic subgroups.

By emphasizing both technical accuracy and clinical relevance, the challenge promotes advancements in breast cancer care that include optimizing NAC regimens, enhancing surgical planning, and reducing disparities in diagnosis and treatment outcomes.

Task description and application scenarios

Briefly describe the application scenarios for the tasks in the challenge.

Task 1: Primary Tumour Segmentation in DCE-MRI

Participants are tasked with segmenting primary tumours in 3D DCE-MRI sequences. Automated tumour

segmentation aids radiologists by reducing manual workload and ensuring consistent delineation of tumour boundaries, which is crucial for treatment planning, response assessment, and surgical guidance.

Task 2: Prediction of Pathological Complete Response (pCR) to Neoadjuvant Chemotherapy (NAC)

This task focuses on developing models to predict the likelihood of achieving pathological complete response or pCR. pCR is defined as the absence of cancer in the breast and axillary lymph nodes confirmed using lesion biopsy of the surgical specimen (residual ductal carcinoma in situ could be acceptable) [5, 6]. Accurate pCR prediction enables oncologists to tailor NAC regimens to individual patients, sparing those unlikely to benefit from unnecessary interventions and guiding alternative therapies. This personalized approach improves treatment outcomes and enhances patients' quality of life.

FURTHER INFORMATION FOR CONFERENCE ORGANIZERS

Workshop

If the challenge is part of a workshop, please indicate the workshop.

The MAMA-MIA Challenge will be hosted as part of the Deep-Breath 2025 Workshop (2nd Deep Breast Workshop on AI and Imaging for Diagnostic and Treatment Challenges in Breast Care). This workshop emphasizes the integration of AI and imaging to address diagnostic and therapeutic challenges in breast care. In collaboration with the ODELIA Challenge, the MAMA-MIA Challenge will be featured as a MICCAI 2025 satellite event. For more details, visit the workshop website: <https://deep-breath-miccai.github.io/deepbreath-2025/>

Duration

How long does the challenge take?

2 Hours

In case you selected half or full day, please explain why you need a long slot for your challenge.

N/A

Expected number of participants

Please explain the basis of your estimate (e.g. numbers from previous challenges) and/or provide a list of potential participants and indicate if they have already confirmed their willingness to contribute.

We expect participation from 10-20 teams cumulatively in both tasks of the challenge. Breast MRI-based method development has been active for both tumour segmentation as well as response prediction themes owing to its importance to treatment planning and outcome prediction pipelines. However, it has been difficult to independently validate their methodologies due to lack of easy-to-access public databases and benchmarks. We believe that this challenge will encourage the community to validate and further develop robust techniques for proposed and related tasks.

Hosting the MAMA-MIA Challenge as part of the Deep-Breath 2025 Workshop is expected to further increase participation by attracting a diverse group of researchers and practitioners interested in AI for breast cancer care. The workshop's focus on fostering collaboration between clinicians and AI experts, alongside its emphasis on clinically relevant topics, will provide an engaging platform for participants, ensuring greater visibility and community engagement.

Publication and future plans

Please indicate if you plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

Upon completing the MAMA-MIA Challenge, our plan is to publish a comprehensive article summarizing the results, key analyses, and insights derived from the challenge outcomes. This collaborative effort will involve the challenge organizing team, clinical and technical collaborators, and the top-performing teams, with each team invited to include up to three co-authors in the paper. The article will provide an in-depth evaluation of the models, their performance, and fairness across demographic subgroups, as well as highlight the broader implications for breast cancer research and clinical applications.

To ensure a transparent and impactful dissemination of the findings, participants are encouraged to publish their individual methodologies and results to the Deep-Breath MICCAI 2025 Workshop or after the release of the official challenge outcome paper. These independent publications will complement the main article by further exploring innovative approaches and unique contributions.

Looking ahead, the MAMA-MIA Challenge dataset and benchmarks will be maintained and expanded to support ongoing research in breast cancer imaging. Future plans include hosting follow-up challenges to address emerging questions, incorporating additional imaging modalities, and refining fairness metrics. Through these efforts, we aim to foster a sustainable research ecosystem that promotes reproducibility, fairness, and impactful advancements in medical AI.

Space and hardware requirements

Organizers of on-site challenges must provide a fair computing environment for all participants. For instance, algorithms should run on the same computing platform provided to all.

The platform used to run the competition will be Codabench, enabling an efficient and transparent evaluation process while fostering reproducible research practices. The training dataset, hosted in the MAMA-MIA Synapse repository [1], has a size of approximately 80 GB. During the validation and testing phases, participants will submit their algorithms encapsulated in Docker containers, ensuring compatibility and seamless execution. The computing environment will be standardized to Linux systems equipped with NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3090 GPUs (24GB memory), providing ample computational power for handling large-scale medical imaging data and complex AI algorithms. All submitted algorithms will be executed on the same computing platform, ensuring uniform hardware and software configurations for reproducibility.

All technical details, including submission guidelines, dataset access, and evaluation protocols, will be provided on the official challenge website. This setup guarantees a streamlined workflow, facilitating equitable participation and robust model assessment.

TASK 1: Primary Tumour Segmentation in DCE-MRI

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

The MAMA-MIA Challenge introduces a benchmark for automated segmentation of primary breast tumours in DCE-MRI, addressing the critical need for robust, accurate, and equitable AI solutions in this domain. By reducing manual workload, improving consistency, and providing precise delineation of tumour boundaries, this task aims to enhance clinical workflows and support individualized treatment strategies.

The training dataset consists of 1506 annotated DCE-MRI studies from diverse demographics and imaging protocols, fostering the development of generalizable models. To ensure cross-site robustness, the evaluation is conducted on a separate dataset of 574 cases from three European centres with varying imaging protocols and clinical settings. Participants leverage multi-phase DCE-MRI sequences to capture tumour kinetic properties and enhance segmentation accuracy.

Fairness is a core component, with models assessed for consistent performance across demographic subgroups, including age, menopausal status, and breast density. Recent studies underline the importance of considering these factors in model development. For instance, Müller-Franzes et al. [3] demonstrated that lower fibroglandular tissue density correlates with reduced segmentation accuracy, emphasizing the need to account for breast density. Similarly, Burten et al. [4] observed that breast density decreases with age and is generally lower in postmenopausal women, further highlighting the importance of incorporating demographic variations. By integrating these insights, the MAMA-MIA Challenge promotes the creation of equitable and generalizable models that ensure robust segmentation performance across diverse populations, setting a new standard for breast MRI analysis and advancing breast cancer care.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

breast cancer, primary tumour segmentation, DCE-MRI, generalizability, fairness, personalized treatment, ethical AI, medical imaging, healthcare equity.

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Lidia Garrucho (1), Kaisar Kushibar (1), Smriti Joshi (1), Maciej Bobowicz (2), Xavier Bargalló (3), Paulius Jaruševičius (4), Karim Lekadir (1, 5)

(1) Artificial Intelligence in Medicine Lab (BCN-AIM), Universitat de Barcelona, Barcelona, Spain

(2) 2nd Dept. of Radiology, Medical University of Gdansk, Gdansk, Poland

(3) Servicio de Radiología, Hospital Clínic, Barcelona, Spain

(4) Kauno Klinikos, Kaunas, Lithuania

(5) Institució Catalana de Recerca i Estudis Avançats (ICREA), Barcelona, Spain

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Lidia Garrucho, email: lgarrucho@ub.edu

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline.

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

Deep-Breath Workshop at MICCAI 2025: 2nd Deep Breast Workshop on AI and Imaging for Diagnostic and Treatment Challenges in Breast Care (<https://deep-breath-miccai.github.io/deepbreath-2025/>)

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

Codabench

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

<https://www.ub.edu/mama-mia>

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic.

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

Publicly available data is allowed

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

The top five teams and the Best Paper Award winner will:

- Be invited to deliver oral presentations (in-person or online) at MICCAI 2025 Deep-Breath Workshop.
- Be invited to contribute to a challenge summary publication.
- Receive official certificates in recognition of their achievements.

Prizes:

1st Position: €400

2nd Position: €300

3rd Position: €200

Best Paper Award: €300 (Shared with Task 2)

This award celebrates innovative solutions that address generalizability and ensure equitable performance across demographic subgroups. To be eligible for the Best Paper Award, participants must submit their findings to the Deep-Breath Workshop. The best paper, as determined by the workshop and challenge committee.

Open-Source Requirement:

All top-performing teams are required to make their code publicly available on GitHub to promote transparency, reproducibility, and community collaboration. Teams that do not submit a paper to the Deep-Breath Workshop describing their method must provide a technical report detailing the implemented methodology to remain eligible for awards.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

The top 3 performing teams will be privately contacted regarding their results. The final ranking, along with the winner of the Best Paper Award (if any eligible in this task), will be officially announced during the MICCAI event.

Performance Results:

Teams may opt out of having their individual performance metrics published by notifying the organizers in advance. However, rankings for the top 3 teams in each task will be made public.

Acknowledgments and Transparency:

All participating teams will be acknowledged for their contributions, fostering innovation in breast cancer research.

A detailed leaderboard will be published (with anonymized results for teams opting out of public disclosure).

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

Upon completing the MAMA-MIA Challenge, we will publish a comprehensive article summarizing the results, key analyses, and insights derived from the challenge outcomes. This collaborative effort will involve the challenge organizing team, clinical and technical collaborators, and the top-performing teams, with each team invited to include up to three co-authors in the paper. The article will provide an in-depth evaluation of the models, their performance, and fairness across demographic subgroups, as well as highlight the broader implications for breast cancer research and clinical applications.

To ensure a transparent and impactful dissemination of the findings, participants are encouraged to submit their work to the Deep-Breath Workshop. These independent publications will complement the main article by further exploring innovative approaches and unique contributions.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Algorithm container submission on Codabench.

Submission instructions will be defined in the challenge Codabench webpage.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

1) Sanity-Check Submissions:

Teams are permitted to make unlimited sanity-check submissions using a small subset of 10 cases from the training set. These submissions are intended solely for debugging and initial testing purposes and will not be considered in the final results.

2) Validation Submissions:

Teams may submit their algorithms for validation on unseen data up to once per day. The validation set comprises 58 cases from the three centres included in the external test set. These submissions allow participants to evaluate and fine-tune their algorithms based on validation performance. However, validation submissions will not contribute to the final test results. To mitigate the risk of overfitting, each team is limited to a maximum of 7 validation submissions.

3) Final Test Submission:

Each team is allowed one final submission to evaluate their algorithm on the unseen test set. This submission will determine the official challenge rankings and results. The final submission must be completed before the official submission deadline, and no resubmissions will be permitted thereafter.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)

- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Registration opens: upon acceptance (March 10, 2025)

Release date of the training cases: upon acceptance (March 10, 2025)

Sanity Check Phase: April, 2025

Validation Phase: April, 2025

Last submission: July 31, 2025

Results analysis: August 2025 (Challenge winners will be contacted to invite them to MICCAI 2025)

Associated workshop days: pending (September 23 and 27, 2025)

Winners announcement during the Deep-Breath workshop at MICCAI 2025.

All phases close at 23:59h of the day indicated (CEST time zone).

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

Informed consent was obtained from all subjects at their respective institutions, and the protocol for using the data was approved by the institutional review board of the data-contributing institution.

The training images from The Cancer Imaging Archive (TCIA) follow their standard licensing (<https://wiki.cancerimagingarchive.net/display/Public/Data+Usage+Policies+and+Restrictions>).

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

Code relative to the MAMA-MIA training dataset and the challenge scoring formulas will be made available in the MAMA-MIA GitHub repository: <https://github.com/LidiaGarrucho/MAMA-MIA>.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Code Submission Requirement:

All participants are required to submit their algorithm code in a Docker container for evaluation purposes. The code should be self-contained and able to run on the provided competition platform without requiring additional setup.

Code Access for Reproducibility:

After the final results are published, top-performing teams will be required to make their code publicly accessible. This promotes transparency and allows other researchers to replicate the results. Participants will be given the option to host their code on a public platform such as GitHub, GitLab, or a similar repository. A link to the repository will be provided upon submission of the results.

Code Confidentiality Before Submission:

Teams' code will remain confidential until the official challenge publication. Teams can choose whether they wish to share or publish their code before the challenge results are released, but this will not affect their participation or evaluation during the competition.

Open-source Contributions:

All participants are encouraged to release their code under an open-source license to foster collaboration and knowledge sharing. This ensures that the results of the challenge are accessible to the wider research community and can be built upon for future advancements. Besides releasing the code, participants will have to write a report or submit a paper to the corresponding workshop (Deep-Breath).

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

This project has received funding from the European Union Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreements No 952103 (EUCanImage) and No 101057699 (RadioVal).

No other conflicts of interest.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education

- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Segmentation, Research, Training, MRI, Breast Cancer

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Segmentation.

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The target cohort for primary tumour segmentation consists of patients diagnosed with breast cancer, undergoing dynamic contrast-enhanced magnetic resonance imaging (DCE-MRI) as part of their diagnostic and

pre-treatment evaluation.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The challenge cohort consists of patients with advanced breast cancer that underwent neoadjuvant chemotherapy (NAC) in their treatment planning.

Key inclusion criteria for this task include:

1. Histologically confirmed diagnosis of breast cancer.
2. Availability of pre-treatment DCE-MRI scans.
3. Tumours localized to one breast with clearly visible primary tumour regions.

Exclusion criteria may include prior breast surgery, incomplete DCE-MRI sequences, or scans of insufficient quality.

This cohort is representative of patients for whom accurate tumour segmentation is crucial for treatment planning, including surgical guidance and response assessment.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Pre-treatment dynamic contrast enhanced Magnetic Resonance Imaging (DCE-MRI)

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

1) Bounding Box for Primary Tumour Breast Localization:

For each case, a bounding box is provided for the breast containing the primary tumour, which can be either the left or the right breast. This information is particularly critical as the dataset includes both unilateral and bilateral DCE-MRI scans.

The bounding box helps streamline the segmentation process by focusing algorithm development on the relevant breast, reducing the search space for tumour localization.

2) Primary Tumour 3D Segmentation Masks:

To support the segmentation task, expert-annotated primary tumour segmentation masks will be provided in NIfTI format for the training dataset, enabling participants to accurately identify and isolate primary tumours within DCE-MRI scans and train the segmentation models.

In addition to the bounding box and segmentation mask, shape radiomics features for each primary tumour are included in the imaging data table for the training dataset. These features are valuable for characterizing tumour morphology and may provide complementary insights for algorithm development. The following shape radiomics features are included: SurfaceArea, SurfaceVolumeRatio, Sphericity, VoxelVolume, MeshVolume, Maximum3DDiameter, Maximum2DDiameterSlice, Maximum2DDiameterColumn, Maximum2DDiameterRow, MajorAxisLength, MinorAxisLength, LeastAxisLength, Elongation, Flatness.

3) Additional Imaging Data:

To further enhance model development, a set of supplementary imaging data is provided. These variables capture variations in imaging protocols and clinical settings, enabling participants to assess their models' generalizability across diverse datasets. The following imaging-related variables are included:

Collection Information:

- Clinical site (hidden in the test set)
- Original TCIA collection
- TCIA series UID (only training set)

Scanner Details:

- Scanner manufacturer (e.g., Siemens, GE, Philips)
- Scanner model

Imaging Parameters:

- View (axial/sagittal)
- Bilateral MRI (yes/no)
- Number of imaging phases
- Fat suppression (yes/no)
- Field strength

Technical Imaging Details:

- Echo time
- Repetition time

Additional Metadata:

- Acquisition times

In real world, the information above is included in the DICOM header, however, the NIFTIs do not contain this metadata. Therefore, these additional imaging information will be available at test time in a standardised JSON or CSV format along with the DCE-MRI sequence for each patient.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

To ensure the evaluation of model fairness across diverse patient demographics and clinical variables, additional patient data will be included only for the training dataset. These variables provide insights into key factors that may influence model performance and outcomes, helping participants identify and mitigate potential biases. The provided variables are:

Clinical Outcomes and Tumour Characteristics

- pCR: Pathologic complete response status (yes/no).
- Tumour Subtype: Classification based on molecular markers.
- Bilateral Breast Cancer: Indicates if cancer is present in both breasts (yes/no).
- Multifocal Cancer: Indicates multiple tumour foci in the affected breast (yes/no).
- HR (Hormone Receptor): Status (yes/no).
- ER (Estrogen Receptor): Status (yes/no).
- PR (Progesterone Receptor): Status (yes/no).

- HER2 (Human Epidermal Growth Factor Receptor 2): Status (yes/no).
- Mammaprint: Molecular risk assessment.
- Oncotype Score: Genomic test score.
- Nottingham Grade: Histologic grade of the tumour.

Demographic and Patient Factors

- Age: Patient's age.
- Menopausal Status: Premenopausal or postmenopausal.
- Breast Density: Density classification based on imaging.
- Ethnicity: Patient's reported ethnicity.
- Has Implant: Presence of breast implants (yes/no).
- Weight: Patient's weight.
- Patient Size: Height or other size-related metrics.
- BMI Group: Body mass index category.

Treatment and Follow-Up Details

- NAC Agent: Neoadjuvant chemotherapy regimen.
- Endocrine Therapy: Status of hormonal therapy (yes/no).
- Anti-HER2/Neu Therapy: Use of HER2-targeted therapy (yes/no).
- Mastectomy Post-NAC: Mastectomy performed after NAC (yes/no).
- Days to Follow-Up: Time elapsed since treatment completion.
- Days to Recurrence: Time until cancer recurrence.
- Days to Metastasis: Time until metastasis occurs.
- Days to Death: Time until death from any cause.

This extensive dataset ensures a comprehensive evaluation of fairness and robustness by enabling the analysis of model performance across subgroups defined by these variables. By addressing potential disparities, the challenge promotes the development of equitable AI solutions for diverse patient populations.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Unilateral or bilateral MRI of the breast region.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The algorithm target is to segment the primary tumor in the pre-treatment DCE-MRI sequence. This segmentation task involves isolating the tumour from surrounding breast tissue, enabling precise tumour delineation that is essential for treatment planning, assessment of tumour characteristics, and response monitoring. The segmentation should include all relevant tumour regions, whether mass-enhanced or non-mass-enhanced, that

may be present in the breast.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy,Robustness,Fairness

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

The imaging modality for the challenge includes pre-treatment DCE-MRI sequences, which are among the most sensitive imaging techniques for evaluating breast cancer and guiding treatment planning. The datasets include pre-contrast and at least two post-contrast images on each DCE-MRI sequence.

Train Dataset:

- Scanner Manufacturers: Siemens (27,3%), GE (64,1%), Philips: (8,6%)

Validation and Test Datasets:

- Scanner Manufacturers: Siemens (26,7%), GE (37,6%), Philips: (35,7%)

A complete table with the imaging distribution of the training and testing datasets can be found on the Challenge website (<https://www.ub.edu/mama-mia/dataset/>).

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

Train Dataset:

The training dataset cohort is built from four public collections available on The Cancer Imaging Archive (TCIA). Namely, level 2b cohort from I-SPY1/ACRIN 6657 trial (I-SPY1) [7], I-SPY2/ACRIN 6689 trial [8, 9], NACT-Pilot [10] and Duke-Breast-Cancer-MRI [11].

The training dataset was annotated by experts for this challenge and is publicly available and hosted on the MAMA-MIA Synapse repository [1] (<https://doi.org/10.7303/syn60868042>). The annotation protocol for the training dataset is described in the MAMA-MIA Dataset publication [2].

General acquisition details:

- Acquisition Plane: Axial (84.4%), Sagittal (15.6%)
- Magnetic Field Strength: 1.5T (72.1%), 3T (27.9%)
- Fat Suppression: Yes (99.6%), No (0.4%)
- Scanner Manufacturers: Siemens (27,3%), GE (64,1%), Philips: (8,6%)

The data is heterogeneous with different imaging protocols and more than 20 clinical sites to facilitate the development of generalizable models. Details about the different acquisition protocols for the included TCIA collections are outlined in the original publications:

ISPY1 [7]: High-spatial-resolution 3D fat-suppressed T1-weighted imaging (≤ 1 mm in-plane resolution) with a gradient-echo sequence (TR ≤ 20 msec, TE = 4.5 msec, flip angle $\leq 45^\circ$, FOV 16–18 cm, matrix 256 x 192, 64 sections, 2.5 mm thickness).

ISPY2 [8, 9]: Images were acquired prospectively at 22+ centers using 1.5T or 3.0T scanners with a breast RF coil, ensuring consistent scanner configuration for each patient.

NACT [10]: DCE-MRI on a 1.5T GE Healthcare scanner with a bilateral phased-array breast coil. The imaging used a high spatial resolution, low temporal resolution, fat-suppressed T1-weighted 3D gradient-recalled echo sequence with 2 mm section thickness. Three time points were acquired (pre-contrast, early, and late phases) with gadopentetate dimeglumine contrast at 0.1 mmol/kg.

DUKE [11]: Retrospective collection of biopsy-confirmed invasive breast cancer patients. DCE-MRI sequences from 1.5T or 3T scanners in the prone position include non-fat saturated T1-weighted and fat-saturated T1-weighted pre- and post-contrast images.

External Validation and Test Datasets:

The testing and validation datasets are private (hidden) and consist of 574 DCE-MRI sequences from three clinical centres across Europe (Spain, Lithuania and Poland).

General acquisition details:

- Plane: Axial (98.8%), Sagittal (1.2%)
- Magnetic Field Strength: 1.5T (59.2%), 3T (40.8%)
- Fat Suppression: Yes (100.0%), No (0.0%)
- Scanner Manufacturers: Siemens (26,7%), GE (37,6%), Philips: (35,7%)

A complete table with the imaging distribution of the training and testing datasets can be found on the Challenge website (<https://www.ub.edu/mama-mia/dataset/>).

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Train Dataset:

Case distribution per original collection:

ISPY1 [7] (TCIA, 1 centre, United States): 171 cases

ISPY2 [8, 9] (TCIA, 22 centres, United States): 980 cases

NACT [10] (TCIA, 1 centre, United States): 64 cases

DUKE [11] (TCIA, 1 centre, United States): 291 cases

Validation and Test Datasets:

The testing and validation datasets are private and consist of 574 DCE-MRI scans from three clinical centres across Europe:

Case distribution per clinical centre:

GUMED (Medical University of Gdansk, 1 centre, Poland): 30 cases

KAUNO (Kauno Klinikos, 1 centre, Lithuania): 232 cases

HCB (Hospital Clinic Barcelona, 1 centre, Spain): 312 cases

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

The patients were diagnosed with locally advanced breast cancer.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

In this challenge, a case represents all data associated with a single patient:

1) Imaging Data:

- Pre-treatment DCE-MRI sequence in NIfTI format, encompassing the pre-contrast phase and at least two post-contrast phases.
- Additional imaging data including the scanner manufacturer, the scanner model, field strength and other imaging variables.

2) Clinical Information: Additional patient data such as demographic factors (e.g., age, menopausal status, ethnicity) and clinical variables (e.g., tumour subtype, treatment outcomes) will be included for evaluating fairness and generalizability of the models. This information is provided only for training and should not directly used for

model training.

3) Annotations:

- **Bounding Box for Primary Tumour Breast Localization:** For each case, a bounding box is provided for the breast containing the primary tumour, which can be either the left or the right breast. This information is particularly critical as the dataset includes both unilateral and bilateral DCE-MRI scans. The bounding box helps streamline the segmentation process by focusing algorithm development on the relevant breast, reducing the search space for tumour localization.

- **Primary Tumour Segmentation Mask (only available in the training set, desired algorithm output):** The case includes expert-annotated primary tumour segmentation masks (either unilateral or bilateral breast, depending on the scan) enabling participants to accurately identify and isolate primary tumours within DCE-MRI scans and train the segmentation models.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

The challenge dataset consists of 2080 DCE-MRI cases:

Training Set: 1506 cases.

Validation Set: 58 cases.

Testing Set: 516 cases.

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

We designed the dataset proportions to ensure a balanced distribution of cases while providing sufficient representation of different demographic groups in the validation and test sets to accurately measure fairness.

Training Set:

The training set consists of 1,506 cases (72.4% of the total), sourced from TCIA. These cases have been annotated specifically for this challenge and provide a robust foundation for model development.

Validation and Test Sets:

The private validation and test sets comprise 574 cases (27.6% of the total) from three European hospitals, ensuring diversity in imaging protocols and populations.

Validation Set Details:

The validation set will include 58 cases, carefully stratified by pCR status, tumour subtype, and hospital of origin to ensure balanced representation. The smaller size of the validation set is intentional, allowing participants to run multiple evaluations efficiently given the GPU resources allocated for the challenge.

Our baseline experiments using nnUNet confirm that inference on the validation set takes approximately 16 minutes, which ensures feasibility for participants across varying computational setups.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

N/A

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

A total of 574 DCE-MRI cases from three European clinical centres (Poland, Lithuania, and Spain) have been newly annotated as part of the EU funded Horizon 2020 project – EuCanImage. These cases will serve as the unseen and private validation and test datasets for the MAMA-MIA Challenge. This inclusion ensures a robust evaluation of algorithm performance on diverse, real-world imaging data that has not been previously accessible, further enhancing the challenge’s impact and generalizability.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

Training Dataset:

The primary tumour was manually segmented in the first post-contrast DCE-MRI image. A baseline nnUNet was used to provide initial automatic segmentation of the primary tumour, which were then corrected by a group of 16 expert clinicians from 10 different institutions around Europe, Asia and Africa. More details regarding the annotation protocol can be found in the MAMA-MIA dataset publication [2]. The training dataset and the annotations are publicly available in the MAMA-MIA Synapse repository [1].

Testing and Validation Dataset:

The primary tumours were segmented by 6 clinicians from the corresponding clinical centres (GUMED, KAUNO, and HCB) using as reference the subtraction DCE-MRI image (first-post contrast minus pre-contrast phases) in a commercial collaborative annotation tool (CMRad – member of EuCanImage consortium). Radiologists used semi-automatic segmentation tool (called SmartPaint) included in CMRad [12] to ease the process and reduce segmentation time.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

Training Dataset:

The tumour annotations were done in NifTI format in the first post-contrast phase using as reference the subtraction image (first post-contrast minus pre-contrast phases) if needed. All the annotation protocol details are thoroughly explained in the MAMA-MIA dataset publication [1].

Testing and Validation Dataset:

Radiologist could make use of semi-automatic segmentation tool included in CMRad [12] to ease the process and reduce segmentation time. More details, including testimonies from the clinicians, can be found in the related article (<https://about.cmrad.com/articles/innovating-radiology-with-smart-paint-a-game-changer-in-medical-imaging-segmentation>).

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The training dataset was annotated by a group of 18 experts (16 radiologists and 2 expert clinicians) with an average of 10 years of experience in breast cancer from 11 different institutions around Europe Asia and Africa.

The private testing dataset was annotated by 6 expert clinicians and radiologists, two per clinical centre (Spain, Lithuania and Poland), averaging more than 7 years of experience in breast cancer.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

N/A

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

General pre-processing for all cases (Training, Validation, and Test Sets)

1) Conversion to NIfTI Format:

The raw DICOM files were converted to NIfTI format using the pycad library (<https://github.com/amine0110/pycad/tree/main>). This standardization simplifies data handling and ensures compatibility with most computational frameworks.

2) Dataset Harmonization:

- Image Quality Control: Quality checks were performed to exclude scans with significant artifacts or incomplete sequences.
- Clinical and Imaging Data Extraction: Relevant clinical and imaging metadata were extracted from the DICOM headers and integrated into the dataset for downstream analyses.
- Standardized Naming and Folder Structure: A uniform naming convention and directory organization were applied to all sequences for consistent data access.

3) Image Orientation Standardization:

- Sagittal Images: Reoriented to the PSR (posterior-superior-right) coordinate system. This orientation aligns with standard practices in breast MRI sagittal acquisitions, ensuring consistency.
- Axial Images: Reoriented to the LAS (left-anterior-superior) coordinate system, widely used for standardizing axial breast MRI acquisitions.

These orientation adjustments minimize errors due to rotations, preserve anatomical accuracy, and ensure compatibility with computational models tailored to specific acquisition planes.

No additional preprocessing methods, such as bias field correction, intensity normalization (e.g., z-score or

min-max normalization), or voxel resampling, were applied to the dataset. This approach allows participants the flexibility to tailor preprocessing techniques to their specific model requirements, depending on the downstream task.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter- and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

The inter-annotator variability can be one of the prevalent sources of error but that is a known source of error in the medical field and particularly in breast cancer [14]. We expect a minimal error in the mass tumour cases and a higher error in the non-mass enhanced tumour cases. Mass tumour cases have clear contours in the first post-contrast images while the non-mass enhanced tumours are more challenging to segment. This argument is supported by our experiment where we requested seven radiologists to delineate one challenging mass and non-mass tumour respectively in Breast MRI. Segmenting the mass tumour took an average of 4 minutes and there was 0.4536 intersection-over-union between annotators. On the other hand, the non-mass case required 8 minutes on average and showed an even lower intersection-over-union value of 0.3776 between annotators. The metrics were reflected in the qualitative comparisons as well where we observed differences in the annotation styles as well as the approach towards segmenting complex tumour characteristics, e.g. presence of necrotic regions.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

N/A

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

Dice similarity coefficient (DSC)

Normalized Hausdorff distance (NormHD)

To measure the fairness, the average disparities of DSC and NormHD among subgroups of the three fairness variables (age group, menopausal status and breast density) will be used.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

DSC measures the overlap between the predicted segmentation and the ground truth. In biomedical imaging, accurately delineating structures (e.g., organs or tumours) is critical for diagnosis and treatment planning. A high DSC indicates a better match between the predicted and actual segmentation, reflecting robust and reliable predictions in clinical contexts. Overlap accuracy is essential in imaging tasks where even small inaccuracies can have significant downstream effects, such as in radiation therapy or surgical planning.

HD quantifies the boundary alignment between the predicted and ground truth segmentations. Normalizing HD ensures it remains comparable across different scales or imaging scenarios. Precise boundary alignment is crucial in clinical applications where anatomical boundaries (e.g., tumour margins) dictate intervention strategies. HD ensures the segmentation model identifies boundaries accurately, reducing the risk of segmenting the tumour as healthy tissue or vice-versa.

Fairness Metric:

In segmentation tasks, disparities across subgroups (e.g., age, menopausal status, breast density) may reflect biased model performance. Measuring these disparities ensures that segmentation quality is consistent across all demographic and clinical groups. Fair and unbiased segmentation is crucial for equitable care. For instance, if a model performs better on younger patients, older patients might receive suboptimal diagnostic outcomes.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

The ranking score combines two terms:

Primary Tumour Segmentation Score = $(1 - \lambda) \times \text{Performance Score} + \lambda \times \text{Fairness Score}$

λ determines the weight given to fairness. For equal weight to segmentation performance and fairness, we defined $\lambda = 0.5$.

A higher composite score indicates better segmentation accuracy and reduced subgroup disparities. This formula emphasizes both technical performance and fairness, fostering the development of models that are clinically robust and equitable.

1) Performance Score:

Between model prediction (P) and ground truth segmentation (Q):

- Average Dice Similarity Index:

Higher values (closer to 1) indicate better overlap.

$\text{Dice} = (2 \times |P \cap Q|) / (|P| + |Q|)$

- Normalized Hausdorff Distance (NormHD):

HD focuses on boundary accuracy. Lower HD values indicate better boundary alignment.

HD_max: Pre-defined maximum threshold for normalization (e.g., HD_max = 150).

$\text{NormHD} = \text{HD}(P, Q) / \text{HD_max}$

The performance score is the average of DSC and $(1 - \text{NormHD})$:

Performance Score = $0.5 \times (\text{Dice} + (1 - \text{NormHD}))$

2) Fairness Score:

Accounts for disparities in segmentation performance across fairness variables v , where $v \in \{\text{age, menopausal status, breast density}\}$. The fairness score penalizes disparities across groups for each fairness variable v ($|V| = 3$ is the total number of selected fairness variables):

Fairness Score = $(1 / |V|) \times \sum_{v \in V} (1 - D_v)$

Lower disparity between groups indicates a higher degree of fairness.

For a given variable (v), the disparity (D_v) is computed as average of disparities across evaluation metrics:

$D_v = 0.5 \times (D_v^{(M1)} + D_v^{(M2)})$

Where $M1, M2$ are segmentation evaluation metrics (Dice, NormHD).

$D_v^{(Mi)}$ represents the disparity among averages of the variable groups g (e.g. if the variable v is menopausal status, then the groups $g_i \in \{\text{g1: pre-menopause, g2: post-menopause}\}$):

$D_v^{(Mi)} = \max(A_v^{(Mi)}) - \min(A_v^{(Mi)})$

$A_v^{(Mi)}$ is the array of group averages for metric M_i (Dice or NormHD) denoted as $A_v^{(Mi)} = \{a_{(g1)}, a_{(g2)}, \dots\}$

where g_i represents the groups in the fairness variable v (e.g. if v is menopausal status, $g_i \in \{\text{g1: pre-menopause, g2: post-menopause}\}$)

For each group (g_i) and metric (M_i), the group average is: $a_{(g_i)} = (1 / n) \times \sum_{(i=1)}^n M(p_i, q_i)$

Where n is the number of cases in group g_i and $M(p_i, q_i)$ is the value of the evaluation metric for a specific case.

Code to compute the scoring formula will be made available in the MAMA-MIA GitHub repository (<https://github.com/LidiaGarrucho/MAMA-MIA>).

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

Empty segmentations will be handled providing a Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC) score of 0 and a default maximum Hausdorff Distance (HD) of 150 mm to account for incorrect segmentations in bilateral images. If a larger HD is found during the competition, the default maximum value will be replaced by the larger HD. The maximum value was obtained from the automatic segmentation model used to segment the tumours, plus a safety margin.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

To rank submissions for the primary tumour segmentation task, we propose a composite score formula that integrates segmentation accuracy and fairness. This approach rewards models that are both accurate in segmentations and minimize disparities across demographic subgroups, providing participants with a clear understanding of their model's performance and its generalizability across diverse populations and clinical centres.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

Welch's t-test will be used to determine if there is a significant difference in mean segmentation performance with the top-1 segmentation model.

The `scipy` and `scikit-learn` Python libraries were used to compute the statistical tests and evaluation metrics.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

Welch's t-test is a valuable choice when comparing segmentation models, especially when there are concerns about unequal variances and small sample sizes.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

The MAMA-MIA Challenge provides an opportunity to perform in-depth analyses beyond primary evaluation metrics, focusing on key aspects such as:

1) Inter-Algorithm Variability: Examine differences in primary tumour segmentation among submitted methods, identifying patterns and commonalities that drive success or failure in specific cases.

2) Common Problems and Biases: Analyse failure modes, including biases related to demographic factors such as age, menopausal status, and breast density. This helps pinpoint areas for improvement in future algorithm development.

3) Ranking Variability: Evaluate how rankings shift when different weight factors (λ) are applied to the combined performance and fairness scores in the scoring formula. This enables a nuanced understanding of trade-offs between accuracy and equitable model performance.

TASK 2: Prediction of Pathological Complete Response (pCR) to Neoadjuvant Chemotherapy (NAC)

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

The MAMA-MIA Challenge addresses a critical need in breast cancer care: predicting pathological complete response (pCR) to neoadjuvant chemotherapy (NAC) using dynamic contrast-enhanced MRI (DCE-MRI). pCR, defined as the absence of residual invasive cancer post-treatment, is achieved in fewer than 30% of patients, underscoring the importance of individualized treatment planning. Accurate pCR prediction enables oncologists to optimize NAC regimens, avoid unnecessary interventions, and explore alternative therapies for non-responders, thereby enhancing patient outcomes and quality of life.

This task involves leveraging the largest annotated DCE-MRI dataset to date, comprising 1506 studies with NAC outcomes. Models are developed using multi-phase DCE-MRI data, with predictions classified as either achieving pCR (pCR = 1) or exhibiting residual disease (pCR = 0). Importantly, demographic and clinical variables are excluded from model inputs to ensure focus on imaging features while maintaining fairness in subgroup performance. The challenge evaluates algorithms on a private validation set of 574 studies from three European centres, emphasizing accuracy, generalizability, and equity across subgroups defined by age, menopausal status, and breast density. By advancing personalized medicine in breast cancer care, this challenge fosters the development of ethical AI tools that address both clinical and societal needs.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

breast cancer, treatment response, pathological complete response, DCE-MRI, generalizability, fairness, personalized treatment, ethical AI, medical imaging, healthcare equity.

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Lidia Garrucho (1), Kaisar Kushibar (1), Smriti Joshi (1), Maciej Bobowicz (2), Xavier Bargalló (3), Paulius Jaruševičius (4), Karim Lekadir (1, 5)

(1) Artificial Intelligence in Medicine Lab (BCN-AIM), Universitat de Barcelona, Barcelona, Spain

(2) 2nd Dept. of Radiology, Medical University of Gdansk, Gdansk, Poland

(3) Servicio de Radiología, Hospital Clínic, Barcelona, Spain

(4) Kauno Klinikos, Kaunas, Lithuania

(5) Institució Catalana de Recerca i Estudis Avançats (ICREA), Barcelona, Spain

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Lidia Garrucho, email: lgarrucho@ub.edu

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

Deep-Breath Workshop at MICCAI 2025: 2nd Deep Breast Workshop on AI and Imaging for Diagnostic and Treatment Challenges in Breast Care (<https://deep-breath-miccai.github.io/deepbreath-2025/>)

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

Codabench

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

<https://www.ub.edu/mama-mia>

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

Publicly available data is allowed

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

The top five teams and the Best Paper Award winner will:

- Be invited to deliver oral presentations (in-person or online) at MICCAI 2025 Deep-Breath Workshop.
- Be invited to contribute to a challenge summary publication.
- Receive official certificates in recognition of their achievements.

Prizes:

1st Position: €400

2nd Position: €300

3rd Position: €200

Best Paper Award: €300 (Shared with Task 1)

This award celebrates innovative solutions that address generalizability and ensure equitable performance across demographic subgroups. To be eligible for the Best Paper Award, participants must submit their findings to the Deep-Breath Workshop. The best paper, as determined by the workshop and challenge committee.

Open-Source Requirement:

All top-performing teams are required to make their code publicly available on GitHub to promote transparency, reproducibility, and community collaboration. Teams that do not submit a paper to the Deep-Breath Workshop describing their method must provide a technical report detailing the implemented methodology to remain eligible for awards.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

The top 3 performing teams will be privately contacted regarding their results. The final ranking, along with the winner of the Best Paper Award (if any eligible in this task), will be officially announced during the MICCAI event.

Performance Results:

Teams may opt out of having their individual performance metrics published by notifying the organizers in advance. However, rankings for the top 3 teams in each task will be made public.

Acknowledgments and Transparency:

All participating teams will be acknowledged for their contributions, fostering innovation in breast cancer research.

A detailed leaderboard will be published (with anonymized results for teams opting out of public disclosure).

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

Upon completing the MAMA-MIA Challenge, we will publish a comprehensive article summarizing the results, key analyses, and insights derived from the challenge outcomes. This collaborative effort will involve the challenge organizing team, clinical and technical collaborators, and the top-performing teams, with each team invited to include up to three co-authors in the paper. The article will provide an in-depth evaluation of the models, their performance, and fairness across demographic subgroups, as well as highlight the broader implications for breast cancer research and clinical applications.

To ensure a transparent and impactful dissemination of the findings, participants are encouraged to submit their work to the Deep-Breath Workshop. These independent publications will complement the main article by further exploring innovative approaches and unique contributions.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Algorithm container submission on Codabench.

Submission instructions will be defined in the challenge Codabench webpage.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

1) Sanity-Check Submissions:

Teams are permitted to make unlimited sanity-check submissions using a small subset of 10 cases from the training set. These submissions are intended solely for debugging and initial testing purposes and will not be considered in the final results.

2) Validation Submissions:

Teams may submit their algorithms for validation on unseen data up to once per day. The validation set comprises 58 cases from the three centres included in the external test set. These submissions allow participants to evaluate and fine-tune their algorithms based on validation performance. However, validation submissions will not contribute to the final test results. To mitigate the risk of overfitting, each team is limited to a maximum of 7 validation submissions.

3) Final Test Submission:

Each team is allowed one final submission to evaluate their algorithm on the unseen test set. This submission will determine the official challenge rankings and results. The final submission must be completed before the official submission deadline, and no resubmissions will be permitted thereafter.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)

- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Registration opens: upon acceptance (March 10, 2025)

Release date of the training cases: upon acceptance (March 10, 2025)

Sanity Check Phase: April, 2025

Validation Phase: April, 2025

Last submission: July 31, 2025

Results analysis: August 2025 (Challenge winners will be contacted to invite them to MICCAI 2025)

Associated workshop days: pending (September 23 and 27, 2025)

Winners announcement during the Deep-Breath workshop at MICCAI 2025.

All phases close at 23:59h of the day indicated (CEST time zone).

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

Informed consent was obtained from all subjects at their respective institutions, and the protocol for using the data was approved by the institutional review board of the data-contributing institution.

The training images from The Cancer Imaging Archive (TCIA) follow their standard licensing (<https://wiki.cancerimagingarchive.net/display/Public/Data+Usage+Policies+and+Restrictions>).

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

Code relative to the MAMA-MIA training dataset and the challenge scoring formulas will be made available in the MAMA-MIA GitHub repository: <https://github.com/LidiaGarrucho/MAMA-MIA>.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Code Submission Requirement:

All participants are required to submit their algorithm code in a Docker container for evaluation purposes. The code should be self-contained and able to run on the provided competition platform without requiring additional setup.

Code Access for Reproducibility:

After the final results are published, top-performing teams will be required to make their code publicly accessible. This promotes transparency and allows other researchers to replicate the results. Participants will be given the option to host their code on a public platform such as GitHub, GitLab, or a similar repository. A link to the repository will be provided upon submission of the results.

Code Confidentiality Before Submission:

Teams' code will remain confidential until the official challenge publication. Teams can choose whether they wish to share or publish their code before the challenge results are released, but this will not affect their participation or evaluation during the competition.

Open-source Contributions:

All participants are encouraged to release their code under an open-source license to foster collaboration and knowledge sharing. This ensures that the results of the challenge are accessible to the wider research community and can be built upon for future advancements. Besides releasing the code, participants will have to write a report or submit a paper to the corresponding workshop (Deep-Breath).

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

This project has received funding from the European Union Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreements No 952103 (EUCanImage) and No 101057699 (RadioVal).

No other conflicts of interest.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning

- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Diagnosis, Prognosis, Treatment planning, Research, MRI, Breast Cancer

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Classification, Prediction

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The target cohort for this task includes breast cancer patients undergoing neoadjuvant chemotherapy (NAC) as part of their treatment regimen. These patients are selected based on their eligibility for NAC, which is typically prescribed to reduce tumour size, facilitate breast-conserving surgery, and evaluate treatment response.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The challenge cohort consists of patients with advanced breast cancer that underwent neoadjuvant chemotherapy (NAC) in their treatment planning.

Key inclusion criteria for this cohort include:

1. Breast cancer patients receiving NAC prior to surgical intervention.
2. Pre-treatment DCE-MRI scans and corresponding post-treatment surgical pathology reports for pCR determination.
3. Tumours measurable on DCE-MRI and adequately imaged across multiple phases.

Exclusion criteria may include patients who did not complete the NAC regimen, incomplete imaging data, or lack of pathological confirmation of treatment response.

This cohort reflects the clinical need to identify patients likely to achieve pCR, aiding personalized treatment planning and sparing non-responders from unnecessary side effects.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Pre-treatment dynamic contrast enhanced Magnetic Resonance Imaging (DCE-MRI)

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

1) Bounding Box for Primary Tumour Breast Localization:

For each case, a bounding box is provided for the breast containing the primary tumour, which can be either the left or the right breast. This information is particularly critical as the dataset includes both unilateral and bilateral DCE-MRI scans.

The bounding box helps streamline the segmentation process by focusing algorithm development on the relevant breast, reducing the search space for tumour localization.

2) Primary Tumour 3D Segmentation Masks:

Expert-annotated primary tumour segmentation masks will be provided in NIfTI format for the training dataset, enabling participants to accurately identify and isolate primary tumours within DCE-MRI scans.

In addition to the bounding box and segmentation mask, shape radiomics features for each primary tumour are included in the imaging data table for the training dataset. These features are valuable for characterizing tumour morphology and may provide complementary insights for algorithm development. The following shape radiomics features are included: SurfaceArea, SurfaceVolumeRatio, Sphericity, VoxelVolume, MeshVolume, Maximum3DDiameter, Maximum2DDiameterSlice, Maximum2DDiameterColumn, Maximum2DDiameterRow, MajorAxisLength, MinorAxisLength, LeastAxisLength, Elongation, Flatness.

3) Additional Imaging Data:

To further enhance model development, a set of supplementary imaging data is provided. These variables capture variations in imaging protocols and clinical settings, enabling participants to assess their models' generalizability across diverse datasets. The following imaging-related variables are included:

Collection Information:

- Clinical site (hidden in the test set)
- Original TCIA collection
- TCIA series UID (only training set)

Scanner Details:

- Scanner manufacturer (e.g., Siemens, GE, Philips)
- Scanner model

Imaging Parameters:

- View (axial/sagittal)
- Bilateral MRI (yes/no)
- Number of imaging phases
- Fat suppression (yes/no)
- Field strength

Technical Imaging Details:

- Echo time
- Repetition time

Additional Metadata:

- Acquisition times

In real world, the information above is included in the DICOM header, however, the NifTIs do not contain this metadata. Therefore, these additional imaging information will be available at test time in a standardised JSON or CSV format along with the DCE-MRI sequence for each patient.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

To ensure the evaluation of model fairness across diverse patient demographics and clinical variables, additional patient data will be included only for the training dataset. These variables provide insights into key factors that may influence model performance and outcomes, helping participants identify and mitigate potential biases. The provided variables are:

Clinical Outcomes and Tumour Characteristics

- pCR: Pathologic complete response status (yes/no).
- Tumour Subtype: Classification based on molecular markers.
- Bilateral Breast Cancer: Indicates if cancer is present in both breasts (yes/no).
- Multifocal Cancer: Indicates multiple tumour foci in the affected breast (yes/no).
- HR (Hormone Receptor): Status (yes/no).
- ER (Estrogen Receptor): Status (yes/no).
- PR (Progesterone Receptor): Status (yes/no).
- HER2 (Human Epidermal Growth Factor Receptor 2): Status (yes/no).
- Mammaprint: Molecular risk assessment.

- Oncotype Score: Genomic test score.
- Nottingham Grade: Histologic grade of the tumour.

Demographic and Patient Factors

- Age: Patient's age.
- Menopausal Status: Premenopausal or postmenopausal.
- Breast Density: Density classification based on imaging.
- Ethnicity: Patient's reported ethnicity.
- Has Implant: Presence of breast implants (yes/no).
- Weight: Patient's weight.
- Patient Size: Height or other size-related metrics.
- BMI Group: Body mass index category.

Treatment and Follow-Up Details

- NAC Agent: Neoadjuvant chemotherapy regimen.
- Endocrine Therapy: Status of hormonal therapy (yes/no).
- Anti-HER2/Neu Therapy: Use of HER2-targeted therapy (yes/no).
- Mastectomy Post-NAC: Mastectomy performed after NAC (yes/no).
- Days to Follow-Up: Time elapsed since treatment completion.
- Days to Recurrence: Time until cancer recurrence.
- Days to Metastasis: Time until metastasis occurs.
- Days to Death: Time until death from any cause.

This extensive dataset ensures a comprehensive evaluation of fairness and robustness by enabling the analysis of model performance across subgroups defined by these variables. By addressing potential disparities, the challenge promotes the development of equitable AI solutions for diverse patient populations.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Unilateral or bilateral MRI of the breast region.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The algorithm target is to predict the pathological treatment response (pCR) to neoadjuvant chemotherapy (NAC) of the patient given the pre-treatment DCE-MRI sequence. The challenge here is to develop a model that uses the provided DCE-MRI scans to predict whether a tumour has completely responded to treatment (i.e., the absence of detectable tumour cells post-treatment). Accurate predictions are crucial to personalize treatment regimens and minimize unnecessary side effects from ineffective therapies.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy,Robustness,Fairness

DATA SETS**Data source(s)**

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

The imaging modality for the challenge includes pre-treatment DCE-MRI sequences, which are among the most sensitive imaging techniques for evaluating breast cancer and guiding treatment planning. The datasets include pre-contrast and at least two post-contrast images on each DCE-MRI sequence.

Train Dataset:

- Scanner Manufacturers: Siemens (27,3%), GE (64,1%), Philips: (8,6%)

Validation and Test Datasets:

- Scanner Manufacturers: Siemens (26,7%), GE (37,6%), Philips: (35,7%)

A complete table with the imaging distribution of the training and testing datasets can be found on the Challenge website (<https://www.ub.edu/mama-mia/dataset/>).

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

Train Dataset:

The training dataset cohort is built from four public collections available on The Cancer Imaging Archive (TCIA). Namely, level 2b cohort from I-SPY1/ACRIN 6657 trial (I-SPY1) [7], I-SPY2/ACRIN 6689 trial [8, 9], NACT-Pilot [10] and Duke-Breast-Cancer-MRI [11].

The training dataset was annotated by experts for this challenge and is publicly available and hosted on the MAMA-MIA Synapse repository [1] (<https://doi.org/10.7303/syn60868042>). The annotation protocol for the training dataset is described in the MAMA-MIA Dataset publication [2].

General acquisition details:

- Acquisition Plane: Axial (84.4%), Sagittal (15.6%)

- Magnetic Field Strength: 1.5T (72.1%), 3T (27.9%)
- Fat Suppression: Yes (99.6%), No (0.4%)
- Scanner Manufacturers: Siemens (27,3%), GE (64,1%), Philips: (8,6%)

The data is heterogeneous with different imaging protocols and more than 20 clinical sites to facilitate the development of generalizable models. Details about the different acquisition protocols for the included TCIA collections are outlined in the original publications:

ISPY1 [7]: High-spatial-resolution 3D fat-suppressed T1-weighted imaging (≤ 1 mm in-plane resolution) with a gradient-echo sequence (TR ≤ 20 msec, TE = 4.5 msec, flip angle $\leq 45^\circ$, FOV 16–18 cm, matrix 256 x 192, 64 sections, 2.5 mm thickness).

ISPY2 [8, 9]: Images were acquired prospectively at 22+ centers using 1.5T or 3.0T scanners with a breast RF coil, ensuring consistent scanner configuration for each patient.

NACT [10]: DCE-MRI on a 1.5T GE Healthcare scanner with a bilateral phased-array breast coil. The imaging used a high spatial resolution, low temporal resolution, fat-suppressed T1-weighted 3D gradient-recalled echo sequence with 2 mm section thickness. Three time points were acquired (pre-contrast, early, and late phases) with gadopentetate dimeglumine contrast at 0.1 mmol/kg.

DUKE [11]: Retrospective collection of biopsy-confirmed invasive breast cancer patients. DCE-MRI sequences from 1.5T or 3T scanners in the prone position include non-fat saturated T1-weighted and fat-saturated T1-weighted pre- and post-contrast images.

External Validation and Test Datasets:

The testing and validation datasets are private (hidden) and consist of 574 DCE-MRI sequences from three clinical centres across Europe (Spain, Lithuania and Poland).

General acquisition details:

- Plane: Axial (98.8%), Sagittal (1.2%)
- Magnetic Field Strength: 1.5T (59.2%), 3T (40.8%)
- Fat Suppression: Yes (100.0%), No (0.0%)
- Scanner Manufacturers: Siemens (26,7%), GE (37,6%), Philips: (35,7%)

A complete table with the imaging distribution of the training and testing datasets can be found on the Challenge website (<https://www.ub.edu/mama-mia/dataset/>).

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Train Dataset:

Case distribution per original collection:

ISPY1 [7] (TCIA, 1 centre, United States): 171 cases

ISPY2 [8, 9] (TCIA, 22 centres, United States): 980 cases

NACT [10] (TCIA, 1 centre, United States): 64 cases

DUKE [11] (TCIA, 1 centre, United States): 291 cases

Validation and Test Datasets:

The testing and validation datasets are private and consist of 574 DCE-MRI scans from three clinical centres across Europe:

Case distribution per clinical centre:

GUMED (Medical University of Gdansk, 1 centre, Poland): 30 cases

KAUNO (Kauno Klinikos, 1 centre, Lithuania): 232 cases

HCB (Hospital Clinic Barcelona, 1 centre, Spain): 312 cases

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

The patients were diagnosed with locally advanced breast cancer.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

In this challenge, a case represents all data associated with a single patient:

1) Imaging Data:

- Pre-treatment DCE-MRI sequence in NIfTI format, encompassing the pre-contrast phase and at least two post-contrast phases.
- Additional imaging data including the scanner manufacturer, the scanner model, field strength and other imaging variables.

2) Clinical Information:

- Pathological complete response (pCR) to neoadjuvant chemotherapy (NAC) treatment (desired algorithm output).

Additional patient data such as demographic factors (e.g., age, menopausal status, ethnicity) and clinical variables

(e.g., tumour subtype) will be included for evaluating fairness and generalizability of the models. This information is provided only for training and should not directly used for model training.

3) Annotations:

- Bounding Box for Primary Tumour Breast Localization: For each case, a bounding box is provided for the breast containing the primary tumour, which can be either the left or the right breast. This information is particularly critical as the dataset includes both unilateral and bilateral DCE-MRI scans. The bounding box helps streamline the segmentation process by focusing algorithm development on the relevant breast, reducing the search space for tumour localization.

- Primary Tumour Segmentation Mask (only available in the training set): The case includes expert-annotated primary tumour segmentation masks (either unilateral or bilateral breast, depending on the scan) enabling participants to accurately identify and isolate primary tumours within DCE-MRI scans.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

The challenge dataset consists of 2080 DCE-MRI cases:

Training Set: 1506 cases.

Validation Set: 58 cases.

Testing Set: 516 cases.

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

We designed the dataset proportions to ensure a balanced distribution of cases while providing sufficient representation of different demographic groups in the validation and test sets to accurately measure fairness.

Training Set:

The training set consists of 1,506 cases (72.4% of the total), sourced from TCIA. These cases have been annotated specifically for this challenge and provide a robust foundation for model development.

Validation and Test Sets:

The private validation and test sets comprise 574 cases (27.6% of the total) from three European hospitals, ensuring diversity in imaging protocols and populations.

Validation Set Details:

The validation set will include 58 cases, carefully stratified by pCR status, tumour subtype, and hospital of origin to ensure balanced representation. The smaller size of the validation set is intentional, allowing participants to run multiple evaluations efficiently given the GPU resources allocated for the challenge.

Our baseline experiments using nnUNet confirm that inference on the validation set takes approximately 16 minutes, which ensures feasibility for participants across varying computational setups.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

Training set (1506 cases): 69.8% (pCR=0) and 29.2% (pCR=1).

Validation set (58 cases): 67.3 % (pCR=0) and 32.7 % (pCR=1).

Testing set (516 cases): 72.7% (pCR=0) and 27.3% (pCR=1).

The class distribution reflects real-world clinical data while maintaining sufficient representation across subgroups for robust evaluation. In the training, validation, and test sets, the class distribution was kept as close as possible to the real-world distribution while ensuring there are enough samples to measure fairness in the protected groups (age groups, menopausal status and breast density).

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

A total of 574 DCE-MRI cases from three European clinical centres (Poland, Lithuania, and Spain) have been newly annotated as part of the EU funded Horizon 2020 project – EuCanImage. These cases will serve as the unseen and private validation and test datasets for the MAMA-MIA Challenge. This inclusion ensures a robust evaluation of algorithm performance on diverse, real-world imaging data that has not been previously accessible, further enhancing the challenge’s impact and generalizability.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

The pathological complete response (pCR) was defined as the absence of cancer in the breast and axillary lymph nodes confirmed using lesion biopsy of the surgical specimen (residual ductal carcinoma in situ could be acceptable) [5, 6].

pCR = 1: pathological complete response to NAC.

pCR = 0: residual disease or partial response (Note: partial responses are considered pCR = 0).

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

N/A

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

N/A

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

N/A

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

General pre-processing for all cases (Training, Validation, and Test Sets)

1) Conversion to NIfTI Format:

The raw DICOM files were converted to NIfTI format using the pycad library (<https://github.com/amine0110/pycad/tree/main>). This standardization simplifies data handling and ensures compatibility with most computational frameworks.

2) Dataset Harmonization:

- Image Quality Control: Quality checks were performed to exclude scans with significant artifacts or incomplete sequences.
- Clinical and Imaging Data Extraction: Relevant clinical and imaging metadata were extracted from the DICOM headers and integrated into the dataset for downstream analyses.
- Standardized Naming and Folder Structure: A uniform naming convention and directory organization were applied to all sequences for consistent data access.

3) Image Orientation Standardization:

- Sagittal Images: Reoriented to the PSR (posterior-superior-right) coordinate system. This orientation aligns with standard practices in breast MRI sagittal acquisitions, ensuring consistency.
- Axial Images: Reoriented to the LAS (left-anterior-superior) coordinate system, widely used for standardizing axial breast MRI acquisitions.

These orientation adjustments minimize errors due to rotations, preserve anatomical accuracy, and ensure compatibility with computational models tailored to specific acquisition planes.

No additional preprocessing methods, such as bias field correction, intensity normalization (e.g., z-score or min-max normalization), or voxel resampling, were applied to the dataset. This approach allows participants the flexibility to tailor preprocessing techniques to their specific model requirements, depending on the downstream task.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

No sources of error are expected for the desired algorithm output.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

N/A

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

Balanced Accuracy.

To measure the fairness, the disparity of Equalized Odds among subgroups of the three fairness variables (age group, menopausal status and breast density) will be used.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

In clinical prediction tasks, such as predicting pathological complete response (pCR), class imbalances are common (e.g., fewer positive cases). Balanced Accuracy ensures the performance on both majority and minority classes is equally weighted, preventing the model from favouring the dominant class. BAcc Ensures equitable and clinically meaningful predictions, particularly in high-stakes settings like cancer treatment response prediction

Fairness Metric:

Equalized Odds ensures that the true positive rate and false positive rate are consistent across subgroups. This metric directly addresses fairness by ensuring no subgroup experiences systematically better or worse predictions. Predictive tasks like pCR impact treatment decisions. Ensuring fair prediction rates across groups minimizes inequities in treatment efficacy or access.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

The ranking score combines performance and fairness. A higher score indicates better model performance, with higher balanced accuracy and reduced subgroup bias among the fairness variables (age, menopausal status and breast density).

$$\text{pCR Prediction Score} = (1 - \lambda) \times \text{Performance Score} + \lambda \times \text{Fairness Score}$$

λ determines the weight given to fairness. For equal weight to segmentation performance and fairness, we defined $\lambda = 0.5$.

1) Performance Score:

The performance metric chosen is the Balanced Accuracy.

$$\text{Performance Score} = \text{BAcc} = (\text{Sensitivity} + \text{Specificity}) / 2$$

2) Fairness Score:

Fairness Score = $1 - (1/|V|) \times \sum_v \text{[Equalized Odds Disparity]}_v$

$|V| = 3$ is the total number of selected fairness variables: age, menopausal status and breast density.

Equalized Odds Metrics for each fairness variable v ($\text{[Equalized Odds Disparity]}_v$):

For each group g_i (e.g. if the variable v is menopausal status, then the groups g_i { g_1 : pre-menopause, g_2 : post-menopause}), compute:

True Positive Rate (TPR): $\text{TPR}_{g_i} = \text{True Positives}_{g_i} / (\text{True Positives}_{g_i} + \text{False Negatives}_{g_i})$

False Positive Rate (FPR): $\text{FPR}_{g_i} = \text{False Positives}_{g_i} / (\text{False Positives}_{g_i} + \text{True Negatives}_{g_i})$

The Equalized Odds aims for consistency across groups:

$\text{TPR}_{(g1)} \approx \text{TPR}_{(g2)} \approx \text{TPR}_{(g3)}$ and $\text{FPR}_{(g1)} \approx \text{FPR}_{(g2)} \approx \text{FPR}_{(g3)}$

To quantify disparities across groups g_i of the fairness variable v :

$\text{TPR Disparity}_v = \max(\{\text{TPR}_{g1}, \text{TPR}_{g2}, \dots\}) - \min(\{\text{TPR}_{g1}, \text{TPR}_{g2}, \dots\})$

$\text{FPR Disparity}_v = \max(\{\text{FPR}_{g1}, \text{FPR}_{g2}, \dots\}) - \min(\{\text{FPR}_{g1}, \text{FPR}_{g2}, \dots\})$

Combine Disparities:

$\text{[Equalized Odds Disparity]}_v = \text{TPR Disparity}_v + \text{FPR Disparity}_v$

Models with smaller Equalized Odds Disparity are considered fairer.

Code to compute the scoring formula will be made available in the MAMA-MIA GitHub repository (<https://github.com/LidiaGarrucho/MAMA-MIA>).

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

N/A

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

To rank submissions we created a composite score formula that combines sensitivity, specificity, and bias minimization to reward models that are both accurate in their predictions and fair across subgroups. This score will give participants a clear understanding of their model's performance on the main task and how well it generalizes across different demographic groups and clinical centres.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

For classification, McNemar's test will be used to determine if there is a significant difference in performance with the top-1 classifier on the same set of observations.

The scipy and scikit-learn Python libraries were used to compute the statistical tests and evaluation metrics.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

McNemar's test is a suitable statistical test for comparing classification models when dealing with paired binary classification data, offering simplicity and robustness in certain scenarios.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

The MAMA-MIA Challenge provides an opportunity to perform in-depth analyses beyond primary evaluation metrics, focusing on key aspects such as:

1) Inter-Algorithm Variability: Examine differences in predictions among submitted methods, identifying patterns and commonalities that drive success or failure in specific cases.

2) Common Problems and Biases: Analyse failure modes, including biases related to demographic factors such as age, menopausal status, and breast density. This helps pinpoint areas for improvement in future algorithm development.

3) Ranking Variability: Evaluate how rankings shift when different weight factors (λ) are applied to the combined performance and fairness scores in the scoring formula. This enables a nuanced understanding of trade-offs between accuracy and equitable model performance.

ADDITIONAL POINTS

References

Please include any reference important for the challenge design, for example publications on the data, the annotation process or the chosen metrics as well as DOIs referring to data or code.

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Further comments

Further comments from the organizers.

N/A